

AZULENES AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART IX. *cyclopenteno-*
AZULENES: 1:2-TRIMETHYLENEAZULENE

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A synthesis of 1:2-trimethyleneazulene has been described.

The construction of a *cyclopentene* system on to the azulene nucleus may be expected on geometrical considerations to alter the spectral characteristics of the resulting azulene derivative in a manner different from that observed in the case of the corresponding dialkylazulene. In order to investigate this aspect as well as to study other properties, it was decided to synthesise the various *cyclopentenoazulenes*. Theoretically four such compounds (I-IV) are possible.

The synthesis of the 3:4-isomer (II) has the additional interest that though it may be considered as an analogue of acenaphthene, it has two 5-membered rings fused on two vicinal bonds of *cycloheptatriene*; the corresponding system in the case of benzene is unknown* (Braun and Anton, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 145; Braun and Reutter, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 1922). The present communication describes a synthesis of the 1:2-isomer (I); its light absorption properties will be discussed later, when the data on the other isomers are also obtained.

The 1:2-trimethyleneazulene (I) has been synthesised by the ethyl diazoacetate method of Plattner and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 907; 1941, 24, 483; Gordon, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 50, 141; Trieb, Kirchhof and Ziegenbein, *Fortsch. Chem. Forsch.*, 1955, 3, 334). The *cyclopent[a]-indan-4-one* (VII) required for this purpose was prepared by the procedure of Baker and Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 787) with slight modifications which raised the overall yield from 45% to 60%. In connection with the preparation of (VII) the Nazarov cyclisation (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R. Cl. Sci. Chim.*, 1946, 633; 1947, 205; *J. Gen. Chem. Russia*, 1950, 20, 2009, 2079, 2091) of benzoyl- Δ^1 -*cyclopentene* (VI) was also investigated; the cyclisation could not be effected by the usual phosphoric acid-formic acid reagent. Recently Braude and Forbes (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2208) have also failed to synthesise a simple bicyclo[3:3:0]-octane derivative by this procedure. The Clemmensen reduction of (VII) gave the corresponding hydrocarbon (VIII) in 84% yield (cf. Baker and

* The classical Baeyer's strain in the case of 3:4-*cyclopentenoazulene* is less to the extent of 8.6° as compared to 1:7-*cyclopentenoindane* (V). Experiments which may possibly lead to (V) are in progress.

Jones, *loc. cit.*); a crystalline byproduct could be obtained from the distillation residue. This byproduct, which is a hydrocarbon, is possibly derived from the pinacol corresponding to (VII); pinacolic reduction often occurs as a side reaction in the Clemmensen reduction (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 31).

(VI)

(VII: R=O)
(VIII: R=H₂)

(IX)

(X)

The cyclopent[*a*]-indane (VIII) on treatment with ethyl diazoacetate yielded a mixture of esters, which was hydrolysed to the corresponding mixture of acids. This on decarboxylation-dehydrogenation over Pd—C in a special apparatus (Sukh Dev, *ibid.*, 1955, 32, 513) yielded the azulene (I) in a rather poor yield. The non-azulenic portion from this experiment was found to be chiefly acidic in character, which was shown to be resistant to decarboxylation and dehydrogenation. This indicates that the primary product of the Büchner reaction, which in the present case should have a norcaradiene structure (IX and other two isomers), is either resistant to base-catalysed (or thermal) isomerisation (Büchner and Hediger, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3502; Darke and Sweeney, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1946, 11, 67; Badger *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3456; cf. Reid *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, 1193) or isomerises preferentially to an acid of type (X) (Büchner and Schulze, *Annalen*, 1910, 377, 259); the latter possibility is much more likely as the cases of the former type have been met with only polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons, wherein norcaradiene structure is stabilised by the conjugative effect of cyclopropane ring (Badger *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), and moreover, in the present case a structure of type (IX) should have a strong tendency to pass into the quasi-aromatic azulene system on dehydrogenation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The spectra were taken in 93% ethanolic solution on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

cyclopent[*a*]-indan-4-one (VII).—A mixture of cyclopent-1-ene carboxylic acid (39.2 g., 0.35 M; Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 769) and purified thionyl chloride (40 c.c.) was heated on a steam-bath for 25 minutes and then the excess thionyl chloride removed from a bath at 80°-90° under 40-45 mm. The residual crude acid chloride was distilled to furnish a colorless liquid, b. p. 84-85°/30 mm, yield 44 g. (95.6%) (Baker and Jones, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 65-67°/16 mm, yield 78%).

The above acid chloride was taken up in dry thiophene-free benzene (400 c.c.), cooled in ice and with stirring, and treated with coarsely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (133.4 g., 1 M) in three lots during ½ hour. The reaction mixture was stirred at the ice-temperature for 1½ hours and finally refluxed for another 1½ hours and left aside at room temperature (30°) for 2½ hours. The product was poured

onto ice and HCl; the benzene phase was separated and the aqueous part extracted with ether (75 c.c. $\times$ 2). The combined extracts after washing with HCl (1:1, 75 c.c.), water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5%, 100 c.c.) and brine was dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was stripped off and the residue carefully fractionated; after rejecting a purple-coloured fore-run (0.5 g., the colour gradually faded off), the required ketone (VII) was collected as a colorless liquid, b.p. $124-25^\circ/2$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5710, d_4^{25} 1.103, yield 65%; λ_{max} 246 m μ (ϵ , 12610) (Baker and Jones, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. $145^\circ/12$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5740, yield 58%).

cycloPent[*a*]-indane (VIII).—The above ketone (30 g.) in toluene (60 c.c.) was added to amalgamated zinc (from zinc wool 90 g. and mercuric chloride 9 g., water 135 c.c. and HCl 8 c.c.), covered with water (90 c.c.); HCl (conc., 180 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) were added and the mixture gently refluxed for 36 hours. A total of 300 c.c. of HCl (conc.) was added to the mixture over suitable intervals. The product was cooled, ether (75 c.c.) added and the light orange solvent layer separated, which was washed with brine (75 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to afford (VIII) a colorless liquid, b.p. $92^\circ/4$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5460, yield 23 g. (83.6%) (Baker and Jones, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. $73-75^\circ/1$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.5511, yield 76%).

The distillation residue from the above experiment was taken up in benzene (12 c.c.) and the deep orange solution passed through a column of alumina, which was washed with petroleum ether. The deep yellow eluates on removal of the solvent furnished an orange viscous liquid, which on trituration with petroleum ether yielded a solid (1 g., m.p. $210-13^\circ$), crystallisation from benzene—*n*-hexane at 0° yielded almost colorless silky needles, m.p. $214-16^\circ$. (Found: C, 92.3; H, 7.7. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}$ requires C, 92.9; H, 7.1 %).

Condensation of Ethyl Diazoacetate with cycloPent[*a*]-indane.—The above hydrocarbon (15.8 g., 0.1 M) was allowed to react with ethyl diazoacetate (EDA; 5 c.c.) exactly as described elsewhere (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 521). On working up, a fore-run of the unchanged hydrocarbon (12 g.) was obtained and the required ester was collected at $145-65^\circ/2$ mm as a red oil (3.0 g.). The recovered hydrocarbon was treated with EDA (4 c.c.) as before and this condensation was thus carried out for six times in all to finally yield a total of 14 g. of the condensation product and 4.0 g. of recovered hydrocarbon. This material was carefully fractionated to obtain the ester as a yellow liquid, b.p. $152-58^\circ/2$ mm, yield 9.0 g. (Found: C, 78.5; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.7; H, 8.2%).

The above ester (13.0 g.) was saponified by refluxing with potassium hydroxide (10 g. + water 20 c.c.) in alcohol (100 c.c.) for 10 hours. The red reaction mixture was diluted with water (300 c.c.) and extracted with ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) to remove the neutral material. The alkaline solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) and the liberated acid taken up in ether (40 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was flashed off and the residue fractionated to afford the acid as a dark yellow, exceedingly thick liquid, b.p. $165-70^\circ/0.9$ mm, yield 6.6 g. (Found: C, 78.0; H, 7.7. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.8; H, 7.4%).

1:2-cyclopentenoazulene (I).—The dehydrogenation-decarboxylation of the above acid was carried out by the procedure described for 1:8-tetramethyleniazulene (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*). The catalyst bed was packed with 20% Pd—C (0.75 g.) mixed with freshly ignited asbestos (medium size; 1.5 g.) and the above acid (6.0 g.) mixed with 20% Pd—C (0.5 g.) was slowly distilled through the hot bed of catalyst (320°-330°) under reduced pressure (35-45 mm) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, exactly as described before. The blue (towards the end, bluish green) "distillate" was taken up in petroleum ether (15 c.c.) and chromatographed over alumina (Basic/I, 2.3 cm $\times$ 18 cm). The column was washed with petroleum ether till the main blue band was eluted out; this was collected separately (ca. 75 c.c.). A very small bluish green band was left on the column which was washed out with ether (rejected). The column was allowed to dry overnight and next day washed with 5% aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution till no more acidic material could be extracted (125 c.c.).

Removal of the solvent from the blue eluates yielded the azulene (60 mg.). This was taken up in alcohol (3 c.c.) and treated with a solution of trinitrobenzene (60 mg.) in ethanol (3 c.c.). After several hours at room temperature and later at 15°, the crystals were collected, m.p. 120-25°, yield 60 mg. This was recrystallised twice from alcohol (2 c.c.) to yield dark brown needles of the *trinitrobenzene complex*, m.p. 129-31°, yield 30 mg. These crystals dissolve in alcohol with a violet coloration. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 3.9; N, 10.97. C₁₈H₁₂O₆N₃ requires C, 59.8; H, 4.0; N, 11.0%).

Pure 1:2-*trimethyleniazulene* was regenerated from the complex (30 mg.) by chromatography over alumina as described previously (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*). The azulene was purified by distillation at 2 mm from a bath at 160-80° as a deep blue viscous liquid with a violet tinge. (Found: C, 92.6; H, 7.6. C₁₃H₁₂ requires C, 92.8; H, 7.1%).

The sodium carbonate extract on acidification and working up with ether, followed by distillation, yielded an acid (4.0 g.), b.p. 160-65°/0.5 mm. This on passing through the hot catalyst bed as above yielded only an almost colorless "distillate" which was found by chromatography to consist essentially of the unchanged acid; the acid was found to be resistant to dehydrogenation-decarboxylation on distillation at atmospheric pressure with Pd—C.

Benzoyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentene (VI) was prepared by the method of Fuson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1594). The material (b.p. 215-30°/3 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5650, yield 5%), purified by fractionation, was converted into the *semicarbazone* by the pyridine method; two recrystallisations from alcohol yielded long, white prismatic needles, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: N, 18.3. C₁₃H₁₃CN₂ requires N, 18.3%).

Pure benzoyl- Δ^1 -*cyclopentene* was regenerated from the semicarbazone (5.0 g., finely powdered) by refluxing it with oxalic acid (10 g. in 200 c.c. of water) and *n*-heptane (50 c.c.) for 3 hours (*i.e.* when all the semicarbazone had disappeared). Working up in the usual manner yielded the ketone as a colorless liquid, b.p. 125°/2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.5685, yield 90%; λ_{max} 249 m μ (ϵ , 11800) (Baker and Jones, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 143°/12 mm).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was crystallised from alcohol to yield orange-red leaflets, m.p. 171-73°. (Found: N, 16.2. C₁₈H₁₂O₄N₄ requires N, 15.9%).

[Baker and Jones, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 162-63°; this discrepancy in the melting point is understandable since Baker and Jones' procedure for the synthesis of (VI) may be expected to yield a product contaminated to a certain extent with the cyclised ketone (VII)].

When pure benzoylcyclohexene (1.0 g.) was treated with a mixture of formic acid-phosphoric acid, according to the details of Braude and Forbes (*loc. cit.*), the ketone (0.7 g.) was recovered as established by the m.p. (166-68°) of its semicarbazone, which was unaltered on admixture with an authentic sample.

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